

STRENGTHENING OF EDUCATION SYSTEM AND PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION IN EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES SHOWING THROUGH PRACTICE

Ismailova Zuhra Karabayevna¹, Madaminova Sabina Alisher qizi²

¹professor, “TIAME” NRU, ²PhD student, “TIAME” NRU

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Abstract. *Researchers explain a useful approach to bridging the gap between research and practice and thus promoting evidence-informed education. This study examines that research collaboration can influence the reception of research knowledge. It is assumed that the composition of experts from the field and scientists in a research team sends out signals that influence trust in as well as the relevance and applicability of the finding. In a survey experiment with practitioners from the field of adult education the influence of different research team compositions around an identical finding is tested. The results show overall high trust, relevance and applicability ratings with regard to the finding, regardless of the composition of the research team. We discuss the potential importance of additional information about research collaborations for effective knowledge translation and point out the need for more empirical research.*

Keywords: *science and practice relationship, research collaboration, research findings, survey experiment, Bayes factor method.*

The question of whether and how scientific evidence can make educational systems and professional action in educational systems more efficient has been a focus of educational science discourse and research programs for the last decades (Hargreaves, 1999; Slavin, 2004; Nelson and Campbell, 2017; Pellegrini and Vivanet, 2021). In the United States, for example, the No Child Left Behind Act (2002)¹ required programs and teaching methods to be based on scientifically derived research results. The adult education legislation of the United States, Workforce Innovation and Opportunity Act (2014), includes, among other things, the claim to evidence-based education. Practitioners in adult education should thus be supported with scientific knowledge in order to professionalize their skills. Professionalism requires individuals to act with the best available (research) knowledge and to reflect on their actions to improve their professional practice (Thomm et al., 2021). In Great Britain, Hargreaves (1998) in particular called for a stronger evidence-based education at a Teacher Training Agency meeting. Evidence-based approaches in education policy are linked to the expectation that the findings of empirical educational research can serve as a knowledge basis for rational decisions and thereby improve the performance of education systems (e.g., Peurach and Glazer, 2012; Tseng et al., 2017). Repeatedly, programs of evidence-based educational reform challenge empirical educational research (Biesta, 2007; Schrader et al., 2020) to communicate research findings to policymakers and practitioners, thereby contributing to improving actions and decisions (Penuel et al., 2020). However, there is a broad consensus that the communication of research findings and their application in the broad field of education has not been satisfactorily implemented to date (Broekkamp and Hout-Wolters, 2007; Kinyaduka, 2017; Tseng et al., 2017). This much-cited and multifaceted gap between research and practice has led to a controversial debate about

evidence-based approaches in education. For example, the communication of research findings is criticized that it resembles a one-way approach that neglects the need to address practice issues (Tseng et al., 2017). Hargreaves (1999, p. 246) also refers to the contextuality of policy and practice decision-making processes in which scientific evidence is one factor in a complex structure. He therefore suggests using the term evidence-informed instead of evidence-based policy or practice to account for the quality of evidence and other (constraining) contextual factors in these fields of action.

The debate has been going on since the origins of educational science in the eighteenth century, and the relationship of educational science and educational practice (and the gap in between) has become a constitutive element, if not an academic feature, of the field (Biesta, 2007). Roughly summarized, the current discussion on the causes of this gap and solutions to it develops along two strands that show some cross-connections (Broekkamp and Hout-Wolters, 2007). The first strand pursues the argumentation that the results of educational research do not meet the needs of policy and practice with regard to the relevance and quality of content and applicability. The second strand focuses on the requirements and conditions for the reception and use of scientific research in practice.

With regard to the first strand, one needs to consider the quality and quantity of evidence in a given field of research. In the field of adult education—which will be considered in this paper in particular—empirical research activities have only been intensified in the last 50 years (Born, 2011; Rubenson and Elfert, 2015) and there is an ongoing debate about whether methodological approaches are fit to deliver the demand for evidence in the competitive field of empirical educational research (Boeren, 2018; Daley et al., 2018). A large number of non-empirical research and an altogether expandable state of research² can therefore be a valid factor contributing to the gap between adult education research and practice. The gap between science and practice can be described with various formulas: farewell to the ivory tower of science (Hayes and Wilson, 2003), reference to basic research with little practical relevance (Siebert, 1979; Hargreaves, 1998) and a distinction of the two cultures (Fox, 2000; Ginsburg and Gorostiaga, 2001).

Our study focuses on the role of such collaborations to bridge the gap between science and practice. Research collaboration or research practice partnerships are discussed as a promising approach to enhance the use of evidence in practical decision making in education and there is a demand for studies on their conditions of success and outcomes (Coburn and Penuel, 2016; Wentworth et al., 2017). We approach the topic of research collaboration as a potential solution for bridging the science-practice-gap from a large-scale dissemination perspective. We are interested if research collaboration between adult education practice and science has an effect on practitioners' perception of research findings. In this sense, we are not concerned with the use and application of knowledge within specific research collaborations but investigate on the more general level of dissemination of research output and its contribution to knowledge transformation (Cordingley, 2009). More specifically, we are interested if information on one quality aspect of research collaboration—the composition of scientists and practitioners in the research team—affects the reception of research findings. The central questions are: How does collaboration between science and practice within research processes in the field of adult education influence practitioner's (1) trust in research findings, (2) attributed relevance of research findings and (3) applicability of these findings? The analysis is guided by system theory and signal theory. Derived hypotheses are tested with data from a survey experiment, testing varying research-practitioner-constellations, applying

Bayes factor methods. The paper has the following structure: We first derive the hypotheses based on theoretical considerations and research results related to the concept of practice research collaboration (section “Bridging the Gap Between Science and Practice Through Collaboration—Theoretical Perspectives”). Then we present the methodology, design, data basis and method of analysis (section “A Survey Experiment on The Perception of Research Knowledge in a Collaborative Setting”).

In the scientific literature the relationship between (adult education) science and practice is often conceptualized theoretically using hermeneutic procedures to explain the *tension* between science and practice. There is little data on what the relationship actually is (St. Clair, 2004). The tension is a structurally determined distance between the two systems (e.g., Feuer, 2006). Thus, there are numerous reasons for this distance, and just as many challenges arising from it (e.g., Fox, 2000; Broekkamp and Hout-Wolters, 2007). From the perspective of practitioners, research questions are of little *practical relevance*. They consider their role as “experimental objects” and see themselves as barely involved in research or unable to apply research results (e.g., Siebert, 1979; Fox, 2000). Practice often perceives science as an alien theory that is generated in an ivory tower—one that seeks answers to questions of no relevance to practice and that leaves adult education staff and institutions alone with their daily questions (Faulstich, 2015). Practitioners complain that research knowledge does not meet the needs of practitioners and that research does not offer practice-relevant knowledge on specific topics (Dean, 1999). The reception of research knowledge requires a clear presentation and linguistic comprehensibility on the part of the scientific community (St. Clair, 2004; Christ et al., 2019) and an awareness of the practical relevance of scientific questions (St. Clair, 2004).

In general, there is very little research on the extent and quality of practitioners’ use of research knowledge in their practice. The sparse findings are rather sobering. K-12 teachers, for example, show a low engagement with scientific evidence in order to inform their teaching practices (Booher et al., 2020). Surveys with adult education providers show that they perceive the intensive exchange with science as useful. At the same time, they feel that scientific research is not sufficiently interested in practice-relevant issues (Christ et al., 2019). However, if they consider research knowledge as relevant, they are more likely to apply this knowledge (Weiss and Weiss, 1981, as quoted in Huberman, 1994) and even change their practice accordingly (St. Clair, 2004). Thus, with major reservations against its relevance and applicability, scientific knowledge is nevertheless recognized as suitable problem solution by practice (St. Clair, 2004; Christ et al., 2019). Practitioners even demand resources from research to deal with everyday problems (Fox, 2000).

The aim of informing and improving practice has an impact on the type of research and the methodology applied (St. Clair, 2004). In order to reduce the structural distance between science and practice, empirical research demands collaboration in the sense of open and collaborative interaction in the research process (see *design-based research approach* e.g., Anderson and Shattuck, 2012 or see *use-inspired basic research* based on Stokes, 1997; e.g., Feuer, 2006; Goeze and Schrader, 2011). In adult education research, too, one of the central issues of the relationship of research to practice is the low level of exchange with practice on the research topics (e.g., Siebert, 1979; Faulstich, 2015). Huberman (1994), for example, believes that it is necessary for researchers and practitioners to work together on knowledge production. Therefore, various forms of research collaboration can contribute to reduce the gap. We understand *research collaboration* as the collaboration

between scientist and practitioner. Whether research knowledge is actually used, however, is finally decided on the practical side. Practitioners actively determine “what is useful and how it is useful” (St. Clair, 2004, p. 238), and ultimately whether they will deal with research-based information or not. After all, the main barriers are the perception of *applicability* and *relevance* of research knowledge, as well as lack of *trust* in science (van Schaik et al., 2018).

Trust in Science by and in Practice

In the public and in science itself, collaboration between research and practice is sometimes problematized with regard to the openness and independence of research (Besley et al., 2017). If, however, practice is supposed to rely on research knowledge in the sense of evidence-informed education, then practitioners must be able to trust the communication of scientists (Kennedy, 1997). Indeed, trust is an essential element that supports evidence-based decision making within a researcher-practitioner relationship (Wentworth et al., 2017). Trust in science and scientists as a construct has both rational and emotional components. General assessments, for example, show different levels of trust depending on the level of education and political or religious attitudes (Nadelson et al., 2014). Trust attitudes can also vary depending on context and situation, leading to different expectations and different levels of trust in science, on the interests and logics of action in the practical domain (Resnik, 2011) on the practice context and culture (e.g., subjective beliefs and values) or science context (e.g., controversial research findings, researchers’ interests, etc.). However complex and multifaceted, trust is a necessary condition for the transfer of scientific knowledge (Mohajerzad and Specht, 2021). Bormann (2012) argues that the acquisition of scientific knowledge through educational reporting leads to an increase of complexity, which can in turn be reduced by trust.

Against the background of the science-practice gap, our study examines whether information about research collaborations between science and practice influences the reception of research findings in the field of adult education. The dimensions examined—trust in the findings as well as assessments of their relevance and applicability—are central prerequisites for the actual use of research findings in the field. Our survey experiment varied compositions of scientists and practitioners in a research team around an identical finding. With reference to considerations based on system and signal theory, our hypotheses suggested that research-practice collaboration and the ratio between participating scientists and practitioners in the research team makes a difference in the reception of the dimensions studied. According to our results, it does not. On average, the descriptive results on trust in the finding, as well as the assessment of its relevance and applicability, show a positive tendency—regardless of the composition of the research team. On the one hand, the results of the Bayesian models support our assumption that trust does not depend on research collaboration. On the other hand, the results of Bayesian models do not support our assumptions about the influence of compositions within research collaborations on reception by signals. Neither the relevance to practice nor the applicability of research findings is influenced by signals about the composition of researchers and practitioners.

Our results suggest that cooperation between academics and practitioners in research teams may be beneficial for the realization of research but does not *per se* lead to widespread use of practitioners’ research knowledge. It would be worthwhile to further explore whether and how evidence-based action in small-scale settings can spill over into large-scale knowledge-sharing settings. Against this background, the focus could shift from trust in

individual research findings and their origins to trust in media and institutions that act as knowledge brokers to communicate scientific findings to professionals in various educational settings, e.g., clearing houses, practical journals and blogs. Potential spill-over effects of collaborative research results could also be investigated in a more differentiated way with regard to various transfer products from individual projects. Transfer products, such as trainings, textbooks or digital media tailored for practice, are *per se* more application-oriented (Goeze and Schrader, 2011) and could be especially efficient if they were developed in mutual collaboration. The expertise of practitioners on conditions and barriers of the use of research results in the practice of professionals as well as further studies on the user behavior in different professional fields (Henson, 2001; Levin and Rock, 2003) can provide important insights and design information.

Although survey experiments by design promise internal and external validity, by combining experimental designs with representative samples, the application of the method brings limitations and trade-offs for any study based on wbmonitor data. An additional module to the regular question program was enabled, which had a correspondingly limited question program. In form of a classic split-ballot experimental design, the study is limited to the analysis of only one vignette dimension, namely the different composition of actors in a research collaboration. The representation of no or more or less practitioners, respectively, scientists in a research team has only limited informative value for aspects of cooperative research and its potentials. Thus, we are not in a position to test the influence of further relevant characteristics for the description of cooperative research processes (e.g., detailed descriptions of persons involved or descriptions of scope and quality of the involvement) on the reception of scientific knowledge. Likewise, we were unable to vary other factors outside the research collaboration, such as characteristics of the research knowledge (e.g., research methods, scientific language, mode of presentation, etc.).

Furthermore, there is a certain proximity between the two terms “expert” and “scientist” in German. Even though we have added the words “from an adult education institution” to the term “experts,” we cannot rule out the possibility that respondents may also associate the term with a scientific nature. Moreover, future research should take up questions of how the impact of knowledge about collaborations in research processes on reception is influenced by recipients’ characteristics (e.g., general attitudes toward science and/or contextual information on the working environment). Finally, we admit that it cannot be ruled out that the effects could be different in other scientific disciplines. In medical research, for example, cooperation with economically oriented pharmaceutical industries critically affects trust in research. In particular, trust in (educational) science as a complex construct deserves closer examination, which should consider further detailed information of contexts in which research results are produced and contexts in which they are to be used (Mohajerzad and Specht, 2021).

On a more general note, this study counteracts the observation that too little importance is given to the reception of research results (St. Clair, 2004). We think that an expansion of research on the reception of scientific knowledge and its effectiveness in the context of knowledge translation is required. In view of constantly growing empirical research on education, questions of how generated knowledge can be used to inform evidence-based practice in education are receiving relatively little attention. This question should not only be answered conceptually but should also be guided empirically in line with the evidence-informed approach.

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